

1.REFERENCE LOGIC FOR THE PEDOGENESIS COMIC

General Information

The title of the comic is “A Pedogenetic resolution of spacetime paradox”.

Pedogenesis is the scientific term for soil formation. It is a philosophical poetic comic about soil formation, longing for mountains, and interconnectedness of life.

It is a 2-page comic. There is no dialogue; instead, there is a poetic text to accompany the drawings in a few panels.

The drawings are simple, with a limited color palette, creating a calm, serene tone matching the poetic text.

Synthesis

This comic tells the story of soil formation and interconnectedness of life through a woman’s longing for the mountains. The woman is talking to the mountain, emphasizing their physical separation and currently being far from each other. Yet, the woman knows that this separation is not real; by holding soil in her hands, she emphasizes that she is always connected to the mountain throughout space and time. This connection is shown by the soil formation process, starting with the rock pieces falling from the mountain, carried out by the river, approaching the woman, and subjected to weathering and biochemical processes to finally transform into soil, which gives rise to other life forms, including the woman’s life. The story shows multiple time scales, from geological to biochemical processes spread over multiple time scales, hinting that everything is happening simultaneously even when they seem to be separate. This interconnectedness throughout the spacetime continuum is also emphasized by the poetic text, which also mentions the mythological stories about soil formation and biogeochemical cycles to intensify the emotions and provide additional dimensions to make the story richer.

Description of the Panels and Rationale for Meaning Making

Page 1

Page 1 has 3 main rectangular panels laid out into 3 rows. The first 2 panels are the same height, while the third is twice as high, covering the bottom half of the page.

Panel 1:

On the left is a mountain, colored in grey tones. The first sentence begins near the mountain with the word “you” and continues into Panel 2 below. The words are separated by wide, empty spaces as if the text itself is traveling through space and time depicted by a vast blue sky.

Panel 2:

At the right end of the pane is the face of a woman. Her hair is wavy as if moving gently in the air. It is colored in soft orange. Some of her hair is drawn out of the panel frame,

hinting at a sense of freedom. Her head is slightly tilted up, her eyes gazing towards the mountain on the left, as if she is looking at the mountain with her mind and heart.

The text reads: and I are so far away now

This stresses the distance between the mountain and the woman, hence also stressing the longing of the woman for the mountain.

It is not only the panels that tells the story; it is also what happens between the panels, what is anticipated (gutters) that informs about the soil formation process from the mountain to the soil.

Panel 3:

This panel covers the bottom half of the page and contains 2 overlaid panels. At the right edge, the woman is shown from her side view, nude and kneeling. Her arms extend toward the soil. Her hands are shown closer, from the top via a small, square overlaid panel; they are holding soil, colored in orange-brown.

A larger rectangular overlaid panel at the top shows a mountain range. Right beside the panel is a text with words pulled closer together, suggesting that as the woman connects with the soil, the distance in spacetime collapses.

The text reads:

Yet, still so
Close
We are

And continues below the larger overlaid panel, to the left of the woman's hand:

As your past
Is present
In the hand of
Your future

This text next to the woman's hand holding soil is about the soil and cycle of life. It implies how the soil was once the mountain, and she herself will be the future mountain.

Page 2

Page 1 covers the implications of interconnectedness and the cycle of life. Page 2 shows the process of interconnectedness through soil formation.

There are 5 main panels laid out in 4 rows, all of similar height. The first row contains panels 1 and 2. There are also multiple smaller panels overlaid on the main panels and the gaps between them, acting as snapshots through space and time to show movement and transformation.

Panel 1:

The same grey mountain from page 1 stands at the left edge of this panel. 8 small overlaid panels are here and pass through panels 3 , 4, and 5 showing a large rock piece falling from the mountain and being transported by a stream.

Panel 2:

The stream flows diagonally from the right side of the page to the left, starting in the middle of the mountain range and ending at the upper corner of the final panel. The blue tones of the stream suggest a vibrant yet also cold, high-energy movement. As it flows, the stream widens because it is getting closer to the woman (and to the reader), hinted by the orange-brown soil and woman's feet in the final panel.

Panel 3 and 4:

Rock pieces are distributed around the stream against a background of soft, warm grey stone.

In Panel 3, the text reads:

Is this Shiva's Divine dance
Gaia's biogeochemical wisdom?

Overlaid Panels: The bottom of Panel 4 and the top of Panel 5 are overlaid with four smaller panels. The first one is the final snapshot of the rock that fell from the mountain, seen closely with lichens on top. The lichens are colored in orange.

The other three panels depict the transformation: cracks made by lichen acidity and weathering from rain gradually erode the rock. The resulting soil is initially a dark brown with small plants and rock fragments, eventually turning into an orange-brown color. Smaller red images depict microbial activity and the resulting fertility of the ecosystem.

Panel 5:

The whole panel is covered in warm orange-brown soil. In the right corner, the woman's bare feet are seen from above. Her toenails are painted green, hinting at the newly sprouting leaves of a plant, closing the cycle of life.

The final text emphasizes the connection and closure:

Or Pan Gu's decomposing corpse
That I am standing on,
Occupying all times
At this space once.